

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 – GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D7.10: Protocol for scale-up production of valuable bioactive mixtures and compounds from agro-forest waste and by-products

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from M1 to M30
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Deliverable D7.10 Responsible	Stefano Superchi (Unibas)
RM7 Responsible	Stefano Superchi

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

Table 1 - List of Deliverables

NUM	OUTPUTS/DELIVERABLE NAME	TYPE*	SHORT DESCRIPTION	LEAD PARTICIPANT	DISSEMINATION LEVEL **	DUE DATE
D7.1	Data on type, quality, availability, and geographical distribution of agro-forest waste and by-products	R	Report and a database on distribution and availability of biomass suitable for valorization	UNIBAS	PU	M12
D7.2	Delivery of validated extraction protocols according to the treated biomass type	R	Report on validated methodologies for value-added extracts depending on biomass type	UNIBAS	PU	M22
D7.3	Extracts and pure compounds suitable for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.4	Extracts suitable as biopesticides	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.5	Report on bio-chemical characterization of biomass extracts and pure compounds	R		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.6	Biomaterials for bioactive extracts delivery	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.8	Formulates for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications (in collaboration with companies)	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.9	Formulates for agro-chemical applications (in collaboration with companies)	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.10	Protocol for scale-up production of valuable bioactive mixtures and compounds from agro-forest waste and by-products	R	Report on validated methodologies suitable for scale-up and industrial production	UNIBAS	PU	M30

Table 2 - List of Project Milestones

MILESTONE NUMBER	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK MODULES	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
M7.1	Survey on regional scale of the type, quality, availability, distribution of biomass from agro-forest waste	7	8	Report
M7.2	Selection of biomass materials suitable for valorization (at least three)	7	10	Report
M7.3	Validation of extraction protocols for selected matrices and materials	7	12	Report
M7.4	Availability of biomass extracts (at least five) suitable for bio-activity tests	7	16	Material
M7.5	Production of a report on bioactivity of different materials and compounds	7	20	Report
M7.6	Availability of biomaterials for bioactive material delivery	7	26	Material
M7.8	Availability of formulates for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications	7	28	Material
M7.9	Availability of formulates for agro-chemical applications	7	28	Material
M7.10	Protocol for scale-up production of valuable bioactive mixtures and compounds from agro-forest waste and by-products	7	30	Report

INTRODUCTION

The final target of the Research Module 7 activity is the valorization of waste and by-products from the agro-forest industry of Basilicata through the production of valuable chemicals and intermediates for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic, agriculture applications. To this end, during Milestones M7.1 and M7.2 the most promising waste for valorization have been selected taking into account the waste availability, the environmental problems connected to their disposal, and the potential for valorization depending on the valuable metabolites content. In M7.3 the optimized procedures for extraction of bioactive metabolites from grape pomace and pomegranate waste have been reported leading, as reported in M7.4, to suitable amounts of the biomass extracts to carry out studies on their bioactivity. The bioactivity of the recovered waste extracts has been reported in M7.5 identifying in Aglianico grape pomace antioxidant and anti-proliferative properties with high cytotoxicity against HepG2 cancer cells. As far as pomegranate waste is concerned, the total residue extract was found to be the richest in punicalagin and ellagic acid, the most promising bioactive metabolites. In particular, such extract showed very high antiproliferative effect against Cholangiocarcinoma (CCA) a rare but highly aggressive liver cancer, with increasing global incidence and mortality, reducing its viability while having no effect on non-tumoral cells.

For these reason the search for a scale-up protocol was focused on the pomegranate waste, with the aim to obtain larger quantities of the bioactive material to carry out extensive *in-vivo* studies and eventually arrive at therapeutical applications.

1. Protocol for scale-up production of pomegranate waste extracts enriched in valuable bioactive metabolites

Bioactive extracts from pomegranate waste.

As reported in M7.4, traditional ethanol extraction was compared with innovative green bio-based and/or environmentally friendly solvents like natural deep eutectic solvents (NADES), dimethylcarbonate (DMC), and 2-MeTHF solvent. In fact, NADES solvents are generally considered as non-toxic and environmentally friendly solvents. Moreover, NADES solvents extracts could be used as they are in cosmetic preparations, without isolation of the bioactive components. Many different DES were then prepared by mixing Choline Chloride/Glycerol, oxalic acid, Urea, Levulinic acid, lactic acid, ethylene glycol, camphor/menthol (hydrophobic DES) in different molar ratios finding the Choline chloride:glycerol 1:2 mixture as the best NADES solvent.

The extracts composition was investigated by LC-MS and the content of the main metabolites (**Figure 1**) is reported in **Table 1**. Punicalagin and ellagic acid were found as the predominant metabolites in all the extracts. The most efficient solvent for ellagic acid extraction was found to be DMC, while Me-THF showed a very high selective extraction efficiency for punicalagin. Moreover, the extract with DES ChCl:gly (1:2) back-extracted with Me-THF showed a better metabolomic profile compared to the ethanolic reference.

Figure 1. Main metabolites found in total residue extracts.

Table 1. Flavonoids content on total residue extract.

Compound	Ethanol	MeTHF	DMC	ChCl:gly (1:2) retroextract*
Punicalagin	59.59 ± 1.95	<u>253.83 ± 0.55</u>	6.64 ± 0.02	84.58 ± 0.16
Baicalein	0.04±0.01	0.04±0.01	0.04±0.02	<u>0.05±0.01</u>
(-)-Epigallocatechin gallate hydrate	0.17±0.005	<u>0.40±0.01</u>	0.33±0.005	0.20±0.005
Apigenin	0.04±0.005	0.04±0.005	<u>0.06±0.001</u>	0.04±0.005
Phloridzin	0.05±0.005	0.16±0.01	<u>0.38±0.02</u>	0.11±0.003
Ellagic acid dihydrate	1.48±0.04	3.85±0.08	<u>5.34±0.06</u>	1.89±0.03
Gallic acid	0.2±0.005	0.86±0.003	<u>1.24±0.04</u>	0.4±0.007
Hesperidin	<u>0.015±0.001</u>	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ

MeTHF is an eco-friendly bio-based solvent with several applications, never previously used as an extraction solvent for pomegranate. Its pronounced selectivity toward punicalagin makes these extracts particularly interesting since punicalagin is a well-characterized polyphenolic compound exhibiting strong antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, antibacterial, and anticancer activities. Moreover, several investigations have demonstrated its effectiveness in addressing various neurological disorders. Different formulations of punicalagin, such as tannin-enriched fractions, ethanolic extracts, and powdered preparations, have shown beneficial effects in multiple animal models of neurological diseases, thus, an interesting application of the extracts obtained in MeTHF could be the valorization of these residues by testing their potential neuroprotective effects.

For these reasons, the scale-up procedure was optimized by using MeTHF as solvent and comparing the results with the above reported small scale extraction approach.

Experimental procedures.

Small scale procedure (< 1.0g)

Pomegranate Extractions: The exhausted pomegranate waste was grounded in a steel blender and stored in the freezer until its use for the extractions

Extraction with Solvents: 500 mg of grounded pomegranate peel was and mixed with the appropriate solvent at a solid/liquid (S/L) ratio of 1:4 (w/w) in a round bottom flask, then stirred at 40 °C for 120 minutes. The residue was filtered through filter paper and the solvent was removed at reduced pressure.

Analysis: A small aliquot of the extract was filtered through a 0.45 µm membrane and analyzed by LC-MS and ¹H NMR (**Figure 3**). The metabolomic profile of the different extracts is shown in **Table 1**.

Large scale-up procedure (>350 g)

Pomegranate Extractions: The exhausted pomegranate waste was grounded in a steel blender (**Figure 2a**) and stored in the freezer until its use for the extractions

Extraction with Solvents: 350 g of grounded pomegranate peel was mixed with MeTHF (1500 mL) at a solid/liquid (S/L) ratio of 1:4 (w/w) in a 2.0 L glass mini-pilot reactor (**Figure 2b**), and stirred at 40 °C for 120 minutes. The residue was filtered through filter paper and the solvent was removed at reduced pressure yielding **16.0 g** of a red/orange solid.

Thus, the extract was analyzed by ¹H NMR and compared with the extract previously obtained from the above reported small scale procedure (**Figure 4**).

Figure 2. On the left: (a) steel blender for grinding pomegranate waste. On the right: (b) Mini-pilot bech-top reactor equipped with 2.0 L vessel, mechanical stirring, heating circulating bath, Dimroth condenser, and temperature control.

Figure 3. ^1H NMR (400MHz, acetone- d_6) of MeTHF extract on 500mg pomegranate peel.

Figure 4. ^1H NMR (400MHz, acetone- d_6) Small vs Larger scale extractions

As inferred comparing ^1H NMR spectra of crude mixtures in **Figures 3** and **4**, the small and large scale extracts match perfectly in both qualitative and quantitative composition. Therefore, we can confidently assume that the metabolic profile of the MeTHF extract obtained from total pomegranate waste is maintained also after the scale-up to a 350 g scale.

This means, that as shown by the LC-MS analysis in **Table 1**, most of the crude extract is constituted by punicalagin, the most valuable bioactive metabolite of pomegranate.

Studies are ongoing to achieve pure punicalagin from the crude by repeated fractional crystallization.

CONCLUSION

By scaling up and optimizing the procedure for extraction of the total content of pomegranate waste by MeTHF treatment we have been able to achieve multi-gram scale of an extract highly enriched in punicalagin, the most valuable bioactive metabolites of pomegranate.

Punicalagin has shown to exhibit strong antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, antibacterial, and anticancer activities. Therefore, the disclosing of a simple, straightforward and efficient protocol for its obtainment from pomegranate waste is certainly of great interest for the possibility of nutraceutical and/or pharmaceutical applications. In fact, punicalagin is commonly obtained in very low yield from pomegranate peel by ethanolic or methanolic extraction and purified by extensive HPLC chromatography. This make this compound extremely expensive (about 100 USD per 1.0 mg) and then unavailable for practical applications.